

First observation in Hungary: the *Columba palumbus* (Linnaeus, 1758) feeding on cherries (Aves)

Imre Fazekas

Abstract. The author observed wood pigeons (*Columba palumbus* (Linnaeus, 1758)) feeding on cherry (*Cerasus avium* convar. *duracina*) trees in orchards in the city of Pécs in southern Hungary, in late May and the first half of June. They swallowed the semi-ripe and fully ripe fruits whole, feeding in the upper part of the canopy, consuming exceptionally copious quantities of fruit. This is the first observation in Hungary. The study includes 8 original figures.

Keywords. Wood Pigeon, new food source, Hungary

Author's Address: Imre Fazekas | Pannon Institute | 7625 Pécs Magaslati út 24.
E-mail: fazekas.hu@gmail.com | <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4318-3946>

Zusammenfassung. Kirschen sind die am frühesten reifende Obstart in Ungarn. Die ökologischen Gegebenheiten des Landes begünstigen den Anbau von Kirschen. Ihr Ursprungsgebiet ist die Kaukasusregion, von dort aus gelangte sie in die griechischen Stadtstaaten und dann in das Gebiet des Römischen Reiches und eroberte kontinuierlich große Regionen Europas. Ab dem 15. Jahrhundert wurden in vielen Teilen Europas Gartensorten angebaut, und im 17. Jahrhundert wurde sie zu einer der bekanntesten Früchte.

Sie ist eine Steinfrucht, die fast überall in der gemäßigten Zone Eurasiens heimisch ist. In ungarischen Gärten ist sie sehr verbreitet. Die wichtigsten Anbauggebiete sind das Gebiet Eger-Gyöngyös im nördlichen Mittelgebirge, die Gegend um Szeged in der Tiefebene, das Nordufer des Plattensees, der südliche Teil von Nyírség in Ostungarn und die Gegend um Buda, Magyar-décse (Mezőség). Ungarische Kirschen waren bereits Ende des Mittelalters berühmt.

Der Erhaltungszustand der Ringeltaube in Ungarn: Erhaltungszustand in Ungarn Holztauben dürfen in Ungarn während der Brutzeit nicht bejagt werden. Die ungarischen Populationen sind nicht gefährdet, die Zahl der Individuen nimmt in mehreren Regionen deutlich zu und ist daher stabil. Besondere Schutzmaßnahmen sind nicht erforderlich. Sie ist ein so genannter Kurzstreckenzieher, der den Winter in den Mittelmeerregionen verbringt, aber auch in milderen Wintern überwintert, insbesondere in den südlichen Inselbergen des Landes.

Der Autor beobachtete Ende Mai und in der ersten Junihälfte Ringeltauben (*Columba palumbus* (Linnaeus, 1758)) beim Fressen von Kirschbäumen in Obstgärten in der Stadt Pécs in Südungarn. Sie verschlangen die halb- und Vollreifen Früchte im Ganzen und ernährten sich hauptsächlich im oberen Teil der Baumkronen. Sie verzehrten sehr große Mengen an Früchten. Dies ist die erste Beobachtung in Ungarn. Die Studie enthält 8 Originalfotos.

Introduction

Cherries (*Cerasus avium* convar. *duracina*) are one of the earliest ripening fruit species in Hungary. The ecological features of the country favor its cultivation of cherries. Its place of origin is the Caucasus region, from where it entered the Greek city-states and then the territory of the Roman Empire and continuously expanded across major regions of Europe. Garden varieties were cultivated in many parts of Europe from the 15th century, and by the 17th century, they had become one of the best-known fruits.

It is a stone fruit, now found everywhere in the temperate zone of Eurasia. It is quite common in Hungarian gardens. Its most important productive regions are the Eger-Gyöngyös area in the Northern Central Mountains, the area around Szeged in the lowlands, the northern shore of Lake Balaton, the southern part of Nyírség in Eastern Hungary, and the area around Buda, Magyardecse (Mezőség). Hungarian cherries were already famous at the end of the Middle Ages.

According to the literature, cherries are particularly rich in vitamins A, B1, B2, B6, folic acid, pantothenic acid, niacin, biotin, and riboflavin. as well as having a significant vitamin C content of 10-15 mg/100 g. Amongst various minerals and trace elements, they contain phosphorus, calcium and sodium, cobalt, a relatively high 190-220 mg of potassium, and iron. Consequently, cherries are judged to be beneficial for the development and health of teeth and bones and are an ideal treat for the developing and ossifying body of children.

The Wood Pigeon is a polytypical species with a Palaearctic distribution. The nominotypical subspecies *C. p. palumbus* occurs throughout Europe, except in Scandinavia and northern Russia, and its nesting range extends into North Africa, Asia Minor and Central Asia, and East and Western Siberia.

In the Hungarian ornithological literature, I could not find any publication in which the authors reported that Wood Pigeon was a voracious eater of cherries in domestic gardens. A summary of the food sources of the Wood Pigeon in Hungary is as follows.

According to Székessy (1973), the Wood Pigeon in Hungary feeds on weed seeds. It is considered a pest in power farms because it consumes many pine seeds and beech acorns. In spring it snaps off fresh buds. There is no mention of cherry consumption in the Hungarian-language book edited by Haraszthy (2000). According to him, its main food is weed seeds, but it also eats all kinds of plant food, such as *Robinia pseudoacacia*, *Japanese acacia*, and elderberries. They have also been observed feeding on tiny slugs and earthworms.

According to Farago et al. (2019), the Wood Pigeon is an herbivore, specialised for seed consumption. In agricultural fields, it picks up a wide variety of weed seeds, grains of crops (e.g., peas) that are maturing or have been lost from harvest, as well as sown seeds, potentially causing damage. It also eats the green parts of cultivated plants (rape, lucerne, and some weeds). In forests, it eats the fruit of forest trees, the cotyledons of trees and shrubs as well as the tender shoots and seeds of pine trees, the latter also being picked from the cones. Sometimes it also eats worms, snails (presumably for calcium consumption), and large numbers of moth adults and pupae (e.g., *Tortrix viridana*). Naturally, the Wood Pigeon, like all pigeon species, feeds its young on "breast milk" The stomachs of Hungarian and Romanian Wood Pigeon (n=18) contain sunflower, feed barley, rice, wheat, peas and maize seeds, *Trifolium*, *Lathyrus*, *Setaria*, *Vicia*, *Polygonum* and *Atriplex* spp., and *Setaria lutescens*, *Bilderdykia convolvulus* and *Echinochloa crus-galli* seeds found at Rékási & Sterbetz (1991).

New observations

In the second half of May and early July 2023, I observed wood pigeons feeding on the semi-ripe or fully ripe fruit of cherry trees in the upper canopy level in the gardens of the town of Pécs in the Mecsek Mountains of southern Hungary. The fruit was torn off the stalk and swallowed whole. The wood pigeon never went into the canopy, but always walked on the horizontal branches and fed on the fruit available there. If there was a crop on the tree, the wood pigeons would walk up the tree, taking almost all the fruit they could.

The Blackbird (*Turdus merula*) was the first to start eating the fruit of the cherry trees. They continued to pick the fruit. These plucked fruits slowly began to decompose. At this time, *Vanessa atalanta* (Linnaeus, 1758) [Red Admiral] butterflies appeared en masse and sucked the decaying fruit during the day. The butterflies spent the night in exceptionally large numbers in the canopy. In addition to the blackbird and wood pigeon, jay (*Garrulus glandarius*) was a regular predator on cherry trees. Their cherry consumption was like that of a wood-pigeon, but jays would scour the entire canopy in search of food.

I should note here that the house sparrows were constantly searching the cherry trees, and the black thrushes were pecking the fruit right down to the stone seed. So, they finished eating the whole crop.

Data on Wood Pigeon populations in Hungary (see Faragó et al. 2019). In Hungary, national population data are difficult to determine due to regional differences in population density.

Figs 1-5. In the upper image (1) the town of Pécs on the southern slopes of the Mecsek mountains, with gardens. The Wood Pigeon feeding on the cherry tree (2-4). In the lower picture the Atalanta butterfly (5)

Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Cherry tree feeding bird species and butterfly species:

1. Blackbird,
2. house sparrow,
3. Wood Pigeon,
4. Jay,
5. Collared dove.
6. Red admiral.

The species in the picture took all the fruit they could.

Similar pest observations are not yet known in Hungary.

The red admiral fed on the damaged cherry fruit throughout the day, retreating into the canopy shelter at night.

Conservation status in Hungary

Data on Wood Pigeon populations in Hungary (see Faragó et al. 2019). In Hungary, national population data are difficult to determine due to regional differences in population density. The estimated nesting population size was 40 000–50 000 pairs in the 1990s (Magyar et al. 1998) and 77 000–110 000 pairs in the early 2000s (MME Nomenclator Committee 2008). For the period 2000–2012 the estimate was 49 000–116 000 pairs

Wood Pigeons cannot be hunted in Hungary during the nesting season. The Hungarian populations are not endangered, and the number of individuals is increasing significantly in several regions and is therefore stable. No special conservation intervention is necessary. It is a so-called short-distance migrant species, spending the winter in the Mediterranean regions, but it can also be found overwintering in milder winters, especially in the southern island mountains of the country. This is in stark contrast with Great Britain, where the Wood Pigeon is regarded as an agricultural pest in arable regions. Thousands are shot by farmers every year and wild-killed birds are sometimes offered for sale in the larger supermarkets in some regions (pers. comm. Colin Plant).

Remarks. In the older Baranya County (Mecsek Mountains) literature, I must mention the name of Ede Agárdi, one of the most famous old bird researchers of the Mecsek Mountains, who wrote about the species in 1940: "I can call it our rare bird. It nests in the forest and far away in the fields."

Horváth (1953) wrote after 10 years of research: "This is not the bird of the Mecsek. I have never found it nesting, nor seen it during the breeding season". Molnár (1984) considered it a sporadic breeder, breeding in Magyaregregy, Váralja, Nagymányok, Zengővárkony and Mecseknádasd. Bankovics (2006) also reported a few observations. The author of this article has added the following comment to his publication: "Since the mid-1990s, it has become a frequent nesting bird in the Komló area. They have been nesting continuously on the 60-year-old spruce of the Majális Square in Komló."

Very interesting are the observations from a mountain area of southern Spain where the diet of Wood Pigeons in was quantitatively assessed monthly during 2011 and 2012. The birds were sampled on their way to roost sites after they had finished feeding and the contents of their crops were subsequently analysed. Twenty plant species and five snail species were identified in the diet. The consumed items varied significantly between seasons. Thus, acorns of *Quercus* sp. were the most consumed item during winter, cereals dominated the summer diet, and tree fruits predominated in spring and autumn. The Wood Pigeons showed a preference for cereals and acorns rather than tree fruits and pasture vegetation. They showed considerable plasticity in their feeding habits since they were able to change the main food item consumed over an abbreviated period and fed on most of the typical Mediterranean tree fruits (see Gutiérrez-Galán et al. 2017). Cherries are not mentioned in the Spanish studies.

The Ukrainian authors Pesotskaya et al (2020) conducted extensive research in the Kharkiv region (Kupiansky, Dvurechansky, Borovsky and Shevchenko districts) and Lugansk (Svatovsky district): they found that Wood pigeons preferred *Morus nigra* and fed it to chicks.

Acknowledgements: I would like to thank my colleague Colin Plant (UK-Bishops Stortford) and Alec Harmer (UK-Lymington) for proofreading and adding language. Thank you to Zsolt Kalotás Hungary, Tolna, for drawing my attention to several literary data. Finally, I thank Péter Gergely (H-Csobánka) for the useful information.

Fig. 7. Distribution of wood pigeons in Hungary, in 2018/2019 (based on the National Game Management Database). The geographic location of the populations is clearly shown on the map. The study population (Baranya County) is found in the forested Mecsek Mountains, and a significant part of the population has moved from the forest edges into orchards and urban parks. The number of local populations in the city of Pécs increases significantly every year, this is due to the rich food source. The map clearly shows that the Wood Pigeons' most important habitats are in lowland areas. Mostly between the Danube and Tisza Rivers, The black circle marks the Mecsek mountain range (see text for details).

Fig. 8. Geographical distribution of the Wood Pigeon (see map for explanation of the colours) (© <https://anotherbirdblog.blogspot.com/2017/01/pigeon-post.html>). With additions and modifications by the author.

References

- Agárdi E. 1940: A Keleti-Mecsek madárvilága. – *Aquila* 46–49: 269–299.
- Bankovics A. 2006: A Mecsek madárvilága / The birds of the Mecsek Mountains. – *Folia Comloensis* 15: 317–360.
- Faragó S. Jánoska F. & Juhász L. 2019: Az örvös galamb (*Columba palumbus*) kezelési terve Magyarországon. – *Hungarian Small Game Bulletin* 14: 47–68.
- Gutiérrez-Galán A., Alonso González I. C. & Maroto de Mercado J. 2017: Woodpigeon (*Columba palumbus*) diet composition in mediterranean Southern Spain. – *Ardeola* 64(1): 17–30
- Haraszthy L. (ed.) 2000: Magyarország madarai / Birds of Hungary. – Mezőgazda Kiadó, Budapest, 441 p.
- Magyar G., Hadarics T., Waliczky Z., Schmidt A. & Bankovics A. 1998: Nomenclator Avium Hungariae. Magyarország madarainak névjegyzéke. Madártani Intézet – MME – Winter Fair, Budapest-Szeged. 202 p.
- Molnár I. 1984: Komló és környékének madárvilága / Birds of Komló and its surroundings (Aves). – *Folia Comloensis* 1: 129–143
- Horváth L. 1953: The Ornis of the Mecsek Mountains Based on Oecologic and Oologic Researches. – *Annales Historico naturales Musei nationalis* 4: 211–225.
- Pesotskaya V.V., Chaplygina A. B., Shupova, T.V., & Kratenko R.I. 2020: Fruit and berry plants of forest belts as a factor of species diversity of ornithofauna during the breeding season and autumn migration period. – *Biosystems Diversity*, 28(3), 290–297. doi:10.15421/012038
- Peterson R.T., Mountfort G. & Hollom P.A.D. 1972: Európa madarai / Birds of Europe. – Gondolat, Budapest, 355 p.
- Rékási J. & Sterbetz I. (1991): Ungarische und rumänische Angaben zur Ernährung wilder Tauben- und Turteltauben-Arten. *Miscellanea Zoologica Hungarica* 6: 67–75.
- Székessy V. 1973: Aves | Madarak. – *Fauna Hungariae XXI*. – Akadémiai Kiadó, Budapest. VII + 448 p.
- Welk, E., de Rigo, D., Caudullo, G., 2016. *Prunus avium* in Europe: distribution, habitat, usage, and threats. In: San-Miguel-Ayanz, J., de Rigo, D., Caudullo, G., Houston Durrant, T., Mauri, A. (Eds.): *European Atlas of Forest Tree Species*. Publ. Off. EU, Luxembourg, e01491d+
- [https://kertlap.hu/korai-gyumolcsunk-cseresznye/\(09.06.2023\)](https://kertlap.hu/korai-gyumolcsunk-cseresznye/(09.06.2023))
- https://forest.jrc.ec.europa.eu/media/atlas/Prunus_avium.pdf (90.06.2023)